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Teachers' Views on the Reputation of the Teaching Profession¹

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Abstract

This study aims to obtain teachers' views on the reputation of the teaching profession, to determine the factors that affect the reputation of the profession positively and negatively through these views. The research was conducted as a phenomenological study from qualitative research methods. The study group of the research consists of 35 teachers selected among the teachers working in the central districts of Ankara in the 2023-2024 academic year. The personal information of these teachers was collected through a demographic information form, and then their views on the reputation of the teaching profession were obtained through a semi-structured interview consisting of 5 questions. As a result of the research, opinions that teaching is a reputable profession, opinions that teaching is not a reputable profession, factors that positively affect the reputation of teaching profession, factors related to personal characteristics that positively affect the reputation of teaching profession, social and environmental factors that positively affect the reputation of teaching profession, factors related to personality that negatively affect the reputation of teaching profession, environmental factors that negatively affect the reputation of teaching profession and suggestions for improving the reputation of teaching profession were determined.

Keywords: Professional Reputation, Teaching Profession, Teaching Professional Reputation, Qualitative Study.

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1. Introduction

Occupation is one of the factors determining a person's social status in the social stratification system, i.e. his/her reputation in the eyes of society. The qualities that an occupation confers to an individual depend on his/her permanent membership of the occupational group, not temporarily, but at least for a reasonable period of time during which he/she can acquire such qualities. There is a connection between the position of a profession in the hierarchy and its social significance. There is also a connection between the social meaning of a profession and its function of organization and control. According to Max Weber, social prestige is expressed in a certain way of life that everyone in society wants to achieve. The income provided by the profession affects the quantitative aspect of the individual's lifestyle. The education required by higher professions also brings about changes in tastes, interests, goals, manners and speech. The social environment and thus the lifestyle changes due to occupational activity. For centuries, the teaching profession has been recognized as one of the most respected professions in many parts of the world. Teaching is a profession whose mission is to educate the future generations of the country. It is the teacher who transfers the knowledge he/she has acquired to new generations and who transfers to his/her students the experiences and accumulations of the civilization and humanity to which they belong (Özoğlu, Gür, & Altunoğlu, 2013). This profession, which aims to serve and benefit society, has gained the respect of almost all people. However, changing living conditions and technological developments have led to changes in the teaching profession globally; especially in recent years, the opportunity to access information easily has changed the perspective of the teacher in the eyes of students and society (Mutluer & Yüksel, 2019).

The success of those practicing the profession and the results obtained are directly linked to some facts. One of these is the society's view of the profession and the status of the profession. Today, it would not be difficult to say that the status and reputation of the teaching profession has changed compared to the past and this change is not in a positive direction. A teacher with a low social status and reputation cannot be expected to have the desired effect on students (Özkale, 2016).

The teaching profession is of great importance as it plays a key role in shaping the future of a country and even the world as a whole. There is a strong two-way relationship between the reputation of those practicing this profession and the preference of the profession. While a high level of reputation ensures that the profession is preferred and the quality of those practicing the profession increases, the increase in the quality of teachers stands out as one of the factors that increase the reputation of the profession.

In addition, the fact that teachers are valued as they deserve is an important factor that increases their motivation to do their profession in the best and right way. A teacher's good social, cultural and economic position in the society ensures professional success. For this reason, it is important

to investigate the social status of the teaching profession in our country, public perception of the profession, general characteristics of the teaching profession, and the factors determining the status of the profession.

In this context, it is necessary to carry out research and studies to determine how the reputation of the teaching profession is in a society and to carry out activities to improve the reputation of the teaching profession, and to take necessary steps in line with the results of these studies.

Reputation

In all societies, individuals want to be valuable and reliable, to be respected and to have prestige. These are the values that reveal a person's reputation. Occupational choice is closely related to social reputation. For this reason, individuals consider the social reputation of the profession when choosing a profession. According to Köksalan (1999), today, profession is seen as an important social phenomenon with psychological, socio-economic and cultural values. It is psychologically important in the sense that it reflects the individual's interests, abilities and achievements to his/her professional life, and socio-economically important in the sense that it affects his/her status, prestige, income and life in society.

The concept of reputation can be handled under three main headings: personal reputation, employee reputation and organizational reputation.

- **Person Reputation:** Personal reputation is defined by Raub and Weesie (1990: 90) as “the qualities and characteristics attributed to a person by others”.
- **Employee Reputation:** Employee reputation is the position of employees in the eyes and minds of their colleagues, managers and organization owners, regardless of their level and status in the organization (Keser, 2012: 152).
- **Organizational Reputation:** Corporate reputation is defined as “the perceived representation of an organization's past actions and future image that shapes its overall image among all its target audience and competitors.” (Bahar, 2019).

Teaching Profession Reputation

Education, briefly defined as the process of raising human beings, is generally defined as planned and deliberate activities carried out in order to reach or achieve certain goals based on the trainable characteristic of human beings (Oğuzkan, 1981). Human beings, who are born with certain abilities, are capable of receiving education. People with this characteristic can become superior to the situation they are in through education. For this reason, expectations from education have been in the direction of raising human beings in all respects. The healing and nurturing aspect of

education is a fact accepted by almost everyone. This acceptance also emphasizes the goal of education to raise good people. It is an expression of this acceptance that there should be a difference between those who receive education and those who do not, and that this difference will be revealed by the qualities of being a good person. Since education pursues such a goal, it is a field of science that stands out with its value-based characteristics rather than its objectivity. In addition to education being a value-based field, the fact that the values that education will bring to people will be useful in the individual and social spheres has turned into an optimism that increases the power of education on people.

The teacher is a behavioral engineer. In order to be able to show the desired results in the workplace and fulfill the tasks assigned to him/her, he/she needs to acquire some qualifications related to his/her profession through education. The teaching profession can be considered an auxiliary profession like the health profession. Teachers are authorized to raise the young generations entrusted to them by using the opportunities of the society. They are responsible for maximizing the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values of their students within the framework of social expectations (Özkale, 2016).

The Varkey GEMS Foundation (2013) created an index that includes different variables from different perspectives to determine the place and value of the teaching profession in society and how society views teachers. The variables included in the index are as follows: The reputation of the teaching profession compared to other professions. Social status of teachers. Parents' encouragement of their children to become teachers. Students' respect for teachers. Public opinion about the adequacy of teachers' salaries. Social opinion about how teachers' salaries would change in light of students' performance. The degree of public trust in the education system. Public trust in the quality of education that teachers provide to students. The strength of teachers' unions. While the variables in this index reveal society's perspective on teachers, they can also be seen as an indicator of the status of the teaching profession in society and the value society places on teachers. The social, cultural and economic status of teachers in society is one of the indicators of society. Teachers are a mirror reflecting the state of societies. The value societies place on teachers and the teaching profession reflects their level of development (Erzen & Epçaçan, 2018).

There are studies by universities, trade unions and researchers on the reputation of the teaching profession. Gökçe (2016) examined that the changing role of the teacher with changing values in education discredited teachers. It is determined that the use of ALO 147 for different purposes such as personal enmity and political games discredits teachers. Güven and Gökçe (2018), who examined the situation of teachers' feeling free in the profession, determined that teachers feel themselves in obscurity and helplessness in the profession and therefore their professional prestige is low. In addition, Gül and Gökçe (2020) revealed that the reputation of teachers working abroad is low

among both administrators and parents. Ünsal and Bağçeci (2016) found that the social perception of teachers' professional image is at a low level. In a study conducted by Polat, Kayısılı, Aydın (2015), it was found that education policies are not effective, the teaching profession is not seen as a reputable profession by the society, and in another study conducted by Doğan and Bayrak (2019), social perception and media perception were found to be low in the professional image of teachers. It was stated that negative news about teachers in the media had an effect on this situation. In the study conducted by Keskin and Yüceer (2017) on the place of the teaching profession in society, they found that the reasons why the society does not value the teaching profession are the low socio-economic life level of teachers, the absence or non-application of student sanctions, the decrease in the reputation of the teaching profession, the increase in the number of teachers, the decrease in the quality of teacher training, and the intervention of everyone in the teacher's work. In Sunar's (2015) "Professional Reputation Scale" study, which reveals how the reputation of the teaching profession has changed over the years, teaching ranked fourth after being a doctor, professor and judge, while in Sunar's (2020) professional reputation research, it is clearly seen that the reputation of the teaching profession has decreased. In the professional reputation survey, teaching has fallen to 14th place after medical doctor, judge, university professor, pilot, ambassador, governor, dentist, captain, general, lawyer, MP, architect, mayor. In a study conducted by Bozbayındır (2019) to reveal the factors that negatively affect the status of the teaching profession, it was concluded that there are low financial opportunities, insufficiency of personal rights and media publications that negatively affect the reputation of the profession. In the study conducted by Atmaca (2020) to determine the factors affecting the social prestige and image of teachers, it was revealed that according to the opinions of teachers, the inadequacy of professionalism, the decrease in personal rights, negative news reflected in the media and negative political discourses wear out the teacher identity.

In the words of Tess Gerritsen, "Reputation is a fragile thing; a hairline crack can shatter it", so it is important to protect it. When teachers show the necessary sensitivity, no person or organization can damage the social reputation of this profession. It is important for teachers to continue their duties with a strong character and ethical stance in order to protect their professional reputation.

Importance of Research

Özdoğru (2020) investigated the relationship between the instructional leadership behaviors of school administrators and corporate reputation, and as a result of the research, it was revealed that there was a positive relationship between the perception of instructional leadership behaviors of administrators and teachers and corporate reputation.

Kurtuluş (2018), in his study on the views of teachers working in high schools on corporate reputation, collected data by interviewing 15 teachers through a semi-structured interview form

consisting of 6 open-ended questions and sub-questions related to these questions. Although the concept of reputation and status are sometimes used synonymously, they are related but different concepts. Çakmak (2015) stated that status refers to social status, while the concept of reputation is the prestige created by this social status, the influence it builds and the sphere of influence it opens to itself within the social field. In the Encyclopedia of Social Sciences Social/Social Status published by TUBITAK, the concept of status is defined as “a person's position, reputation and prestige in society”. In the same source, the main determinants of status are defined as occupation, family position, class, education, skill, achievement, lineage, race, ethnicity and gender. Aktay (2022) states that status is based on a differentiation within the same profession, group or social structure. In this respect, there are differences between status and reputation. Although there have been limited studies on the status of professions, there are almost no studies on reputation. The most comprehensive study on the reputation of professions is the “Working Life and Reputation of Professions in Turkey” research. This research, which was repeated twice by Lütfi Sunar, the first with the support of TÜBİTAK in 2015 and the second with private means in 2020, is important in that it not only ranks the reputation of 113 different professions, but also reveals the change in the reputation of these professions within 5 years.

Although there are some studies on the status of the teaching profession in the literature, it is seen that there are almost no studies directly on the reputation of the teaching profession.

Yurdakul, Gür, Çevik, Kurt (2016), in their research titled Teaching profession and the status of the profession, based on the opinions of teachers working in the public sector, analyzed issues such as job satisfaction, reasons for choosing the profession, commitment to the profession, complaints, individual and social value perceptions, wage satisfaction, burnout levels, professional autonomy, participation in decision-making mechanisms, working conditions and professional development. Köse and Öztürk (2023) collected data from 478 teachers working in Osmaniye in the 2021-2022 academic year with the “Teaching Profession Image Scale” and conducted interviews with 16 teachers and school administrators in their research in which they aimed to obtain the opinions of teachers and school administrators on the teaching profession image and the contribution of the Teaching Profession Law to the teaching profession image. As a result of the mixed-method study, it was stated that the general opinion of the participants was that the Teaching Profession Law contributed to the image of the teaching profession.

Gümüştaş and Gülbahar (2022), in their study investigating the factors affecting teachers' professional motivation, interviewed 15 teachers working in Buca and Karabağlar districts of İzmir province and revealed the factors affecting teacher motivation in the light of the data obtained.

Yıldırım (2017) aimed to determine the components affecting the reputation of school principals and tried to determine the components affecting reputation in terms of each type of participant in

line with the opinions collected in writing from 171 teachers, 55 school administrators and 135 parents in the city center of Kütahya.

Demir and Hammalı (2020) investigated the factors affecting the reputation of the teaching profession according to the views of teachers, and for this purpose, they interviewed a total of 9 teachers working in Sivas province and districts.

It was seen that the researches conducted were limited in number and covered a narrow region in terms of scope, and in this context, it was evaluated that the research conducted would make a high contribution to the literature in terms of its scope. In addition, it is also recommended to conduct research on the reputation and prestige of the teaching profession in the literature (See: Alabaş, 2011; Eren, Çelik, Oğuz, 2014).

2. Method

Research Model

This research is qualitative in approach. Qualitative research can be defined as research in which qualitative data collection techniques such as observation, interview and document analysis are used and a qualitative process is followed in order to reveal perceptions and events in a realistic and holistic manner in a natural environment (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008). Creswell (2013) identified some situations where the use of qualitative research method is appropriate as follows: Qualitative research is conducted because a problem or issue needs to be explored. This research method is necessary to examine a group or universe, to identify variables that cannot be easily measured, or to listen to the voices left behind. These are better reasons than using established knowledge from the literature or relying on research findings to investigate a problem. Qualitative research is done to provide a detailed understanding of a complex issue. Qualitative research is done to understand the context or environment in which research participants face a problem or issue. It is also preferable to use qualitative research for specific study groups, when there are partial or inadequate theories, or when existing theories fail to reflect the complexity of the problem being studied.

This study was conducted as a phenomenological study, one of the qualitative research designs. Phenomenology, which is a method of examining the reason for the existence of events and defining events at the end of the examination, is also called phenomenology (Baş & Akturan, 2008). Qualitative research is an approach that aims to explore and understand the meanings that individuals or groups attribute to a social or human problem (Creswell, 2013). For this reason, it is frequently used in social sciences. Although there are different reasons for this, it offers the opportunity to examine human beings in an eclectic understanding. Since qualitative research sheds light on this, this management is frequently used in the social and humanities field. Qualitative

research is designed to be more flexible than quantitative research as it offers the advantage of using different data collection methods in the same study (Punch, Oance 2014: 142).

Semi-structured interview is an interview that provides both fixed response options and the opportunity to examine the relevant field in more depth. Such interviews give the interviewee the opportunity to express his/her thoughts in more depth (Büyüköztürk et al. 2014). In addition, Karasar (2012) listed the strengths of the semi-structured interview method as having the flexibility to adapt to changing conditions instantly since there is a direct verbal relationship between people, having an instant and fast feedback mechanism, ensuring that almost everyone, including illiterate people, can be a source of data, and accessing personalized and detailed information. This method also has a high response rate.

Study Group

The study group of the research consists of 35 teachers working in public schools in the central districts of Ankara province in the 1st semester of the 2023-2024 academic year and determined by purposeful sampling method.

Table 1. Participant teachers' gender, professional seniority, education level and branches number and percentage distribution.

<i>Demographic Characteristics</i>	<i>Category.</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Frequency (%)</i>
Gender	Female	23	65,71
	Male	12	34,29
Professional seniority	1 - 5 years	3	8,57
	6 - 10 years	8	22,86
	11 - 15 years	10	28,57
	16 - 20 years	9	25,71
	21 years and above	5	14,29
Education level	License	25	71,43
	Postgraduate	10	28,57
Branch	Turkish	6	17,14
	Mathematics	4	11,43
	Science	5	14,29
	Social Sciences	7	20

	English	3	8,57
	Technology Design	2	5,71
	Preschool	8	22,86
	Altindag	6	17,14
	Keçiören	10	28,57
	Yenimahalle	5	14,29
District	Mamak	4	11,43
	Cankaya	7	20
	Xinjiang	1	2,86
	Etimesgut	2	5,71
	Preschool	5	14,29
	Primary School	12	34,29
	Middle School	1	2,86
	High School	7	20
	Special Education	2	5,71
School/Institution Type	Bilsem	3	8,57
	Guidance and R. C.	2	5,71
	Ministry Central Organization	3	8,57
	Total	35	100

Care was taken to select participants from different districts of Ankara, different branches and different types of schools in order to maximize diversity. Similarly, considering that teachers with different seniority may have different approaches and attitudes, teachers with different levels of teaching experience were included in the study.

Data Collection Tools

In this study, semi-structured interview technique, which is one of the methods of collecting qualitative research data in accordance with the purpose of the research, was used in order to determine the situation regarding teachers' professional reputation through teachers' views.

A form consisting of 5 questions was created to be used in the study, necessary arrangements were made by taking expert opinion about the form, and these questions were directed to the participants in separate interviews with each participant. The semi-structured interview questions are as follows.

- What do you mean by professional reputation?

- Do you think teaching is a prestigious profession?
- What are the factors that positively affect the reputation of teaching?
- What are the factors that negatively affect the reputation of teaching?
- What would you suggest to improve the reputation of teaching?

In addition, a form was created by the researcher to collect demographic information of the participants;

- Gender
- Professional seniority
- District of assignment
- Type of school served

information was collected on the headings.

Data Collection

As stated by Karasar (2012), the most ideal method for data collected by interview method, if the conditions are appropriate, is to keep a voice recording due to its advantages such as re-listening and not missing any point. Audio recording also reduces the risk of interrupting the interview process. Thus, the interview process is not hindered. For this reason, it was preferred to audio record the interviews primarily with the permission of the participants, and the responses of the participants who did not consent to the audio recording were written down in accordance with the permission of the participants. Interviews were conducted one by one in the time period preferred by the participants, in places where they felt comfortable and could express their views clearly, in some cases using online tools. Each interview lasted an average of 20-25 minutes.

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Data Analysis

The data of the study were analyzed using descriptive analysis method. The descriptive content analysis method involves in-depth examination and organization of independently conducted research on a specific topic or field (Akyurt & Ültay, 2021). The aim of this type of analysis is to present the results in an organized and interpretable way. For this purpose, the data obtained are first described in a systematic and understandable way, then these descriptions are explained and interpreted, examined in a cause-effect relationship and certain conclusions are drawn from them. Descriptive analysis consists of four stages: In the first stage, the data analysis is based on the research questions, the conceptual framework of the study and the issues included in the interview or observation. According to this structure, the themes in which the data will be organized and presented are determined. In the second stage, the data received are read and categorized according to the previously created structure. Data are selected for descriptive purposes and collected in a meaningful and logical way. Also at this stage, direct quotations are selected to be used in the

preparation of future results. In the third stage, data are identified and supported with direct quotations if necessary. Finally, the findings are related and explained (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008). In this study, the data were analyzed by following the steps described above.

Validity in descriptive analysis depends on the correct recording of the data obtained, their proper categorization and analysis, and finally their holistic interpretation (Kvale, 1989). Therefore, it is important for the researcher to have an objective attitude towards the topic and to maintain this attitude during the analysis process. In this study, the researcher paid special attention to this issue.

3. Findings

In this part of the study, interview questions were analyzed and teachers' views on the reputation of the teaching profession were examined and the findings were presented.

Teachers' Views on the Concept of Professional Reputation

In order to understand teachers' perceptions of the concept of professional reputation and how they define professional reputation, the first question of the interview was “What do you understand by the word professional reputation?”.

Table 2. The distribution of sub-items (concepts) used to define the concept of “professional reputation” according to teachers.

Sub-elements (Concepts)	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Respect/Respectability	20	85,71
Being valued/Feeling valued	8	22,85
Acceptance	2	5,71
Trust/Reliability	3	8,57
Love	1	2,85
Özen	3	8,57
Place/position in society	2	8,57
Acceptance	2	8,57
Impact/impression	1	2,85

As can be seen from the table, 85.71% of the participants emphasized the concept of being respected in the eyes of the society and being respected in the society while defining professional reputation. Based on this, it can be concluded that teachers think that professions that are respected by the society have a higher professional reputation.

The second most prominent concept is the concept of being valued by the society and being made to feel valuable by other members of the society. 8 out of 35 participants defined being valued as one of the main components of professional reputation.

Some of the participants defined the concept of professional reputation by using more than one sub-element/concept. For example, participant K4 defined the concept of professional reputation as “Reputation comes from prestige, it is the state of being reliable and valuable. Professional reputation also means being respected, valued and trusted.” The participant coded P8 said, “I understand the word 'professional reputation' to mean that the profession is respected and valued in the eyes of the society and that there is trust in that professional”.

Teachers' Views on the Reputation of the Teaching Profession

The aim of the study was to obtain teachers' views on the reputation of the teaching profession and for this purpose, the question “Do you think teaching is a reputable profession?” was asked. The responses to this question were analyzed in two groups as positive and negative opinions. The distribution of teachers who expressed positive and negative opinions is shown in the table below. The views obtained from the participants are presented in Table 3. If participants defined more than one sub-item, each sub-item was included and reflected in the table.

Table 3. Teachers' opinions on whether the teaching profession is prestigious or not.

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Opinion on Reputational Status	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Teaching is a prestigious profession.	18	51,43
Teaching is not a prestigious profession.	17	48,57

As can be seen in the table, teachers' views on the prestige of the teaching profession are almost split in half. While 51.43% of the participant teachers stated that teaching is a prestigious profession, 48.57% stated that teaching is not a prestigious profession.

The sub-items emphasized by the teachers who stated that the teaching profession is prestigious are as follows.

Table 4. Sub-items mentioned by the teachers who stated that teaching is a reputable profession.

Sub-elements (Concepts)	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Raising human beings/Educating society	8	44,44
Being a source of knowledge transfer	2	11,11
Being a trustworthy person	1	5,55
Having a higher reputation than before	8	44,44

44.44% of the teachers who stated that they think that teaching is a prestigious profession associated this situation with teachers' duties of raising people, educating and shaping the society. Of the teachers who expressed positive opinions about the reputation of the profession, 11.11% of them stated that the main reason for this reputation was being the source of knowledge transfer and 5.55% of them stated being a reliable person.

For example, the participant coded P32 said “I think teaching is a prestigious profession. I think it is a prestigious profession because it is a profession that raises generations and educates the society”. The participant coded P27 said “(...) bringing people to the society we live in gives our profession a different reputation.”, while the participant coded P19 explained the source of reputation as “(...) how can a profession that raises future generations, has respectability, saves the nation be disreputable...”.

A striking point here is that even 44.44% of the teachers who think that teaching is a prestigious profession stated that they believe that although it is still a prestigious profession by comparing it with previous years, there has been a decrease in its reputation. The participant coded P28 said, “Although it seems that the value that society gives to teachers has decreased compared to the past, I think teaching is always prestigious.” The participant coded P24 said, “I still think it is a prestigious profession, although not as much as it used to be.” The participant coded P2 explained the situation as “I think that teaching is a reputable profession, but it is not respected, valued, despised and belittled today as much as it used to be.”

As seen in Table 4, 48.57% of the teachers stated that they think that teaching is not a prestigious profession.

Table 5. Sub-items mentioned by teachers who stated that teaching is not a reputable profession.

Sub-elements (Concepts)	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Problems arising from the system/management	4	23,52
Lack of respect/not being valued	8	47,05
Social disruption	3	17,65
Once prestigious but now disreputable	12	70,59

47.05% of the teachers who stated that teaching is not a prestigious profession associated this situation with the lack of respectability of the profession and the lack of value in society. 23.52% stated that problems arising from the system and/or administration led to discrediting, while 17.65% said that social deterioration eliminated the reputation of the profession.

Again, as a remarkable point, 70.59% of the participants who stated that the teaching profession was discredited stated that they used to think that the teaching profession was reputable or reputable, but they do not believe that it is reputable now. For example, the participant coded K15

responded to the question “Do you think that teaching is a prestigious profession?” as “In the past, yes, I used to think so, but now I don't think so.” Similarly, the participant coded P12 answered the same question as “Yes for 50-60 years ago, no for today.” The participant coded P8 said, “It used to be a reputable profession, but I don't think it is like that now.” The participant coded P4 said, “I think the reputation of all professions has been damaged. I think there is a loss of reputation not only in teaching, but also in many professions such as doctor, police, engineering. The respect and value for people has decreased. As a result, the reputation of professions has decreased” and stated that he thinks that the decline in reputation is not limited to the teaching profession.

The participant coded P14 stated that he believes that social degradation has damaged the reputation of the teaching profession by saying “I think that the recent social, media and moral degeneration and deterioration have discredited teaching.” The participant coded P21 emphasized that teachers have become a professional group that is subjected to violence due to the impact of social changes, and the participant coded P18 stated that he thought that the profession had no reputation due to the negative expressions of the administrators, especially the senior level, towards the teaching profession.

Teachers' Views on the Factors Affecting Positive Teaching Reputation

In the interview conducted within the scope of the research, teachers were asked about the factors that positively affect teaching reputation. The factors identified according to the answers given and the distribution of the answers are shown.

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Table 6. The factors that positively affect the reputation of the teaching profession according to teachers.

Factors	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Positive attitudes and behaviors of teachers	12	34,29
Caring about the profession	7	20
Fulfilling responsibilities	6	17,14
Complying with ethical and moral rules	4	11,43
Improving oneself / Being open to improvement	7	20
Having a good education	3	8,57
Knowledge and professional skills	9	25,71
Communication skills	10	28,57
Being a profession that affects the society	11	31,43
Being a sacred profession with a long history	4	11,43
Favorable economic conditions/sufficient wages	6	17,14
Sharing good practices	5	14,28
Healthy execution of the rewarding system	2	5,71
Teachers' supportive attitudes towards each other	4	11,43
Positive attitudes and supportive statements by MoNE/managers	3	8,57

Having a Profession Law	1	2,86
Social rights	2	5,71
City/school/branch of assignment	2	5,71
High budget allocated to education	1	2,86
No positive factor	4	11,43

As a result of analyzing the interviews, 19 factors were identified from the teachers' responses. Eight of these factors belong to personal characteristics. These can be listed as attitudes and behaviors, caring about the profession, fulfilling responsibilities, complying with ethical and moral rules, self-development/being open to development, having a good education, and knowledge and professional equipment. The data related to this is presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Table on the factors related to personal characteristics that positively affect the reputation of the teaching profession according to teachers.

Factors Related to Personal Characteristics	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Positive attitudes and behaviors of teachers	12	34,29
Caring about the profession	7	20
Fulfilling responsibilities	6	17,14
Complying with ethical and moral rules	4	11,43
Improving oneself / Being open to improvement	7	20
Having a good education	3	8,57
Knowledge and professional skills	9	25,71
Communication skills	10	28,57

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The most frequently mentioned factor by the participants ($f=12$) was the teacher's attitude and behavior. The teacher's communication skills were mentioned by 28.57% of the participants, while knowledge and professional equipment were mentioned by 25.71%. Caring about the profession was mentioned by 20%, fulfilling responsibilities by 17.14%, following ethical and moral rules by 11.43% and having a good education by 8.57%.

For example, participant P33 said, "Teaching depends on the attitudes and behaviors of the people who perform the profession. The more a teacher cares about his/her profession, fulfills his/her responsibilities completely, and exhibits professional ethical and moral attitudes while doing so, the more positively the reputation of teaching will be affected." She said. Similarly, the participant coded P22 said, "The factors that positively affect the reputation of teaching are related to the attitudes of the people practicing this profession. If the people who do this profession do their job properly, comply with ethical rules and are conscientiously comfortable, these affect the reputation positively". Participant P13 emphasized the personal qualities of the teacher by saying "Showing

the necessary patience and love towards students, being fair, keeping up with innovations, keeping up with the innovations in the field and trying to improve himself/herself, having high communication skills positively affect the reputation of the teacher”.

Eleven of the 19 factors identified in the study are social and/or environmental factors. These factors are as follows: being a profession that affects the society, being a sacred profession with a deep-rooted history, favorable economic conditions/providing adequate wages, sharing good examples, healthy execution of the rewarding system, teachers' supportive attitudes towards each other, positive attitudes and supportive statements of the Ministry of National Education/Administrators, having a Professional Law, social rights, high budget allocated to education, and the city/school/branch of duty. The data on these are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Social and environmental factors that positively affect the reputation of the teaching profession according to teachers.

Social and Environmental Factors	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Being a profession that affects the society	11	31,43
Being a sacred profession with a long history	4	11,43
Favorable economic conditions/sufficient wages	6	17,14
Sharing good practices	5	14,28
Healthy execution of the rewarding system	2	5,71
Teachers' supportive attitudes towards each other	4	11,43
Positive attitudes and supportive statements by MoNE/managers	3	8,57
Having a Profession Law	1	2,86
Social rights	2	5,71
City/school/branch of assignment	2	5,71
High budget allocated to education	1	2,86

Among these factors, the most frequently mentioned factor is that it is a profession that affects the society with 31.43%. Another 11.43% of the participants stated that the fact that the teaching profession is a deep-rooted and sacred profession positively affects the reputation of teaching. For example, the participant coded p30 said, “The fact that the teaching profession is a sacred profession both socially and religiously since ancient times positively affects the reputation of the profession”. The participant coded P27 explained the factors affecting positively as follows: “(...) I think that being taken as a guide in all areas of society and the fact that your views reach people in waves with the children you educate are positive factors”. Participant p19 emphasized that playing a pioneering and supportive role that develops the society is effective in increasing teacher reputation.

17.14% of the participants stated that favorable economic conditions and adequate salary/wage payment is a factor that positively affects reputation, but they also emphasized that the level of realization of this factor is currently low. For example, participant p9 said “Improving the economic situation of teachers positively affects the reputation of teaching”, while participant p20 said “giving teachers the value for their labor (...) is a factor that affects positively”.

While 14.28% of the participants emphasized the sharing of good examples, 5.71% stated the importance of the reward system, 11.43% emphasized the effect of teachers' supportive attitudes towards each other, and 8.57% emphasized the effect of positive attitudes and statements of the MoNE and administrators. One participant (2.86%) stated that having a professional law and allocating a high budget for education would affect teacher reputation, while two participants (5.71%) stated that social rights and the city, school and branch of work can be counted among the factors that have a positive effect on reputation.

For example, the participant coded P34 said “Positive statements made by administrators, the Minister of National Education about teachers, rewarding teachers, administrators standing by teachers (...) can be factors that positively affect our reputation.”, while the participant coded P8 said “Teachers' achievements, teachers who contribute to the school, students and the region should be rewarded and honored”. The same participant said, “(...) generally, negative situations are shared more on social media and communication tools. Successful examples should be covered more in the media” and underlined the importance of the media in sharing good examples. The participant coded P1 emphasized that “positive examples should increase and be kept in the foreground”, while the participant coded P14 emphasized “the variety of working hours and social rights.

Another interesting point here is that 4 participants (11.43%) responded to this question as “there is no positive factor” or “I cannot think of a positive factor”. Participants were encouraged to think about this issue again, but upon receiving the same answer again, the participants were not insisted upon.

Teachers' Opinions on Factors Affecting Teaching Reputation Negatively

Within the scope of the research, teachers were asked what factors negatively affect teaching reputation. The factors identified according to the answers given and the distribution of the answers are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Factors that negatively affect the reputation of the teaching profession according to teachers.

Factors	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Teachers' negative attitudes and behaviors	7	20
Failure to fulfill professional responsibilities	6	17,14
Failure to comply with ethical and moral rules	3	8,57
Faculties of Education take too many students	4	11,43
Low entrance scores to Faculties of Education	3	8,57
Not keeping up with the age, not improving oneself	3	8,57
Being an easily obtainable profession	6	17,14
The low quality of the education provided by the Faculties of Education	5	14,28
Inadequate economic conditions/salaries	15	42,85
Inadequacy of personal rights and working conditions	4	11,43
Negative impact of the media	8	22,86
Negative discourses of senior managers, school administrators and politicians	7	20
Parents' interference in education and negative discourses	12	34,28
Teacher violence and mobbing	6	17,14
Decline in the quality of education	2	5,71
Blaming the failures in the education system on teachers	2	5,71
Assigning tasks to teachers outside of education	1	2,86
Problems related to curriculum	2	5,71
Teachers' salaries being on the agenda too often	1	2,86
Increased ways of accessing information	1	2,86

As a result of the analysis of the interviews with teachers, 20 factors that negatively affect the reputation of the teaching profession were identified. While only 4 of these factors are related to personal characteristics, 16 of them are related to environmental factors. Another striking point in the negative factors is that 3 factors are directly related to faculties of education. This situation can be considered as an indication that the effect of education faculties on teacher quality is also questioned by teachers.

Personal factors that negatively affect the reputation of the teaching profession can be listed as teachers' negative attitudes and behaviors, not fulfilling the responsibilities required by the teaching profession, not complying with ethical and moral rules, not keeping up with the age/not improving oneself. Data on these factors are shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Personality-related factors that negatively affect the reputation of the teaching profession according to teachers

Personality Related Factors	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Teachers' negative attitudes and behaviors	7	20
Failure to fulfill professional responsibilities	6	17,14
Failure to comply with ethical and moral rules	3	8,57
Not keeping up with the age, not improving oneself	4	11,43

Of the participant teachers, 20% stated that negative attitudes and behaviors of teachers, 17.14% stated that not fulfilling the responsibilities of the teaching profession as the most important personal factors that negatively affect the reputation of the teaching profession. 3 participants stated that teachers who do not comply with ethical and moral rules and 4 participants stated that teachers who do not keep up with the age and do not improve themselves negatively affect the reputation of the teaching profession.

The participant coded P22 said “Factors such as those who perform the profession not performing their duties fully and not having the stance brought by the profession negatively affect the reputation”, while the participant coded P29 said “The teacher's inability to fulfill the requirements and responsibilities of the profession, not keeping up with the age, and not exhibiting exemplary behavior to his / her environment negatively affect the reputation of teaching”. Similarly, the participant coded P28 listed “(...) not keeping up with the developing age and equipment (...)” among the factors that negatively affect reputation.

Environmental factors that negatively affect the reputation of the teaching profession can be listed as follows: The high number of students enrolled in faculties of education, low entrance scores to faculties of education, low quality of education provided by faculties of education, teaching being an easily obtainable profession, insufficiency of economic conditions/salaries, insufficiency of personal rights and working conditions, negative impact of the media, negative discourses of senior administrators, school administrators and politicians, parents' interference in education and their negative discourses, violence and mobbing against teachers, decline in the quality of education, blaming the failures in the education system on teachers, assigning non-educational tasks to teachers, problems related to the curriculum, teachers' salaries being on the agenda too often, and increased access to information. Data on these factors are shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Environmental factors that negatively affect the reputation of the teaching profession according to teachers.

Environmental Factors	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Faculties of Education take too many students	4	11,43
Low entrance scores to Faculties of Education	3	8,57
Low quality of education provided by the Faculties of Education	5	14,28
Being an easily obtainable profession	6	17,14
Problems arising from the perception of young people who choose teaching as a profession	5	14,28
Inadequate economic conditions/salaries	15	42,85
Inadequacy of personal rights and working conditions	4	11,43
Negative impact of the media	8	22,86
Negative discourses of senior managers, school administrators and politicians	7	20
Parents' interference in education and negative discourses	12	34,28
Teacher violence and mobbing	6	17,14
Decline in the quality of education	2	5,71
Blaming the failures in the education system on teachers	2	5,71
Assigning tasks to teachers outside of education	1	2,86
Problems related to curriculum	2	5,71
Teachers' salaries being on the agenda too often	1	2,86
Increased ways of accessing information	1	2,86

The highest frequency among the environmental factors that negatively affect teaching reputation is the inadequacy of economic conditions and salaries. 42.85% of the participants stated that inadequate teacher salaries are among the factors that negatively affect professional reputation. Another environmental factor that follows this is parents' interference in education and their negative discourses. In this context, both parental intervention in the school and classroom and complaint mechanisms were discussed. Some participants underlined the negative impact of parent satisfaction-oriented education on teacher reputation

It is seen that 20% of the participants emphasized the negative impact of the negative discourse of senior administrators and politicians towards the teaching profession and the non-teacher-friendly attitudes of school administrators on the teaching profession; 17.14% of the participants complained about violence and mobbing against teachers. In addition, 22.86% of the participants emphasized the negative impact of the media.

For example, while the participants coded P31 and P24 emphasized the negative impact of the negative discourses of bureaucrats and politicians on the reputation of the profession, the participant coded P1 said, "(...) the inclusion of social media in education life, the loss of the officiality of the teacher-parent relations through social media and their deterioration negatively

affect the reputation of the profession.” The participant coded P11 answered “(...) violence, mobbing, administrators who cannot defend the teacher against the parents (...) negatively affect it”, while the participant coded P8 emphasized the effect of negative news reflected in the media. Similarly, the user coded P16 underlined that social media prepares the environment for parents to intervene in education by saying “(...) the perspective of structures such as social media on teachers is not healthy, parents get power from this”.

As mentioned above, most of the participant teachers emphasized the low salaries of teachers and the participant coded P7 said, “Since we are a formalist society, there is a tendency for people to show respect as much as their salaries. Teachers' salaries reduce respectability. (...) This is one of the important factors.” The participant coded P3 stated that “the fact that teachers are easily complained about and made to feel as if they are under the hand reduces the reputation of teaching”, and the user coded P4 stated that “(...) the salary is inadequate, as much as the salary of a flat civil servant” damages the reputation. One participant said, “I think the factors that negatively affect the reputation of teachers are those related to salaries. Talking about salaries too much discredits the profession.” In his answer, the user coded P2 stated that “(...) students' and parents' attitudes, behaviors and verbal expressions that make them look small, and the fact that senior administrators and ministers do not make arrangements to protect teachers and increase their welfare level have a negative impact.” In addition, the burden of unsuccessful results in the education system is placed on the teacher. Similarly, it was stated that the planning problems of the central administration such as changes in the curriculum, uncertainties arising from the changes and the density of the curriculum put the teacher in a difficult situation

In addition to these, 4 (11,43%) of the participants stated that the excessive number of students in faculties of education, 3 (8,57%) stated that the decrease in the scores of faculties of education as a result of the excessive number of students in faculties of education and therefore the placement of students with lower qualifications in faculties of education, and 5 (14,28%) stated that the inadequacy of the education provided by faculties of education negatively affected the reputation of the profession. The user with the code P30 explained as follows: “It is a negative factor that there are too many admissions to education faculties in universities and the scores are pulled backwards.” The participant with the code P27 questioned the quality of education faculties with the statement “Pedagogical formations of teacher training institutions are insufficient”.

The rate of participants who stated that the perceptions of young people who choose teaching have a negative impact on the teaching profession is 14.28%. For example, the participant coded P26 stated that “Young people look at the profession as a civil service”,

Another issue that participant teachers identified as a factor that negatively affects reputation is that teaching is an easily obtainable profession. Here, points such as the appointment of people from outside the field as teachers (P1), the existence of people who say “If you can't be anything

else, you can be a teacher” (P20), and the appointment of paid teachers were emphasized. The decline in the quality of education was also characterized as a factor that negatively affects the reputation of teaching. The fact that the teacher has lost his/her authority is also among the negative factors mentioned here.

Teachers' Suggestions for Improving Teaching Reputation

The last question posed to the participant teachers in the interview conducted within the scope of the research was “What would you suggest to improve the reputation of the teaching profession?”. The answers given by the teachers to this question were analyzed and categorized and the findings.

Table 8. Teachers' suggestions for increasing the reputation of the teaching profession.

Suggestions	f (Frequency)	% (percent)
Increasing the quality and quantity of teacher trainings	9	25,71
Improving economic conditions	16	45,71
Reducing student enrollment in the faculty of education	2	5,71
Improving the quality of education in faculties of education	4	11,43
Recruiting qualified students to the faculty of education	7	20
Quality and fairness of teacher selection criteria	5	14,28
Top managers, school administrators and politicians respect and value teachers	5	14,28
Taking deterrent measures with protective laws against negative behaviors against teachers	7	20
Raising public awareness with the support of the media and politicians	9	25,71
Improvement of personal and social rights	7	20
Improving working conditions	2	5,71
Developing a Law on Teaching Profession	3	8,57
Increased authority and initiative of teachers	3	8,57
Preventing parental interference in education	7	20
Ensuring discipline at school	4	11,43
Not assigning teachers out of their field of study	2	5,71
Rewarding teachers	1	2,86
Weeding out incompetent teachers	1	2,86
Involvement of teachers in training planning processes	1	2,86
Taking out-of-field responsibilities from teachers	1	2,86

Most of the participant teachers suggested improving economic conditions. 47.71% of the teachers considered the improvement of teacher salaries and other wages as a measure that would increase the reputation of the teaching profession. Another point emphasized by teachers is the increase in the quality and quantity of teacher trainings. This issue was mentioned by 25.71 percent of the participant teachers. There are 3 different points emphasized by teachers here: The first one is the

inclusion of trainings on teacher duties and responsibilities, the second one is the inclusion of trainings in the field of profession, and the third one is the inclusion of trainings for personal development. Another issue related to teacher trainings is the need to improve the content and quality of teacher trainings.

For example, the participant coded P32 said, “People who are practicing this profession, especially newcomers, can receive training on professional ethics, responsibilities and teacher stance”, while the participant coded P9 stated that in-professional courses should be increased and qualified.

Among the suggestions of the teachers, evaluations regarding faculties of education were also included. 5.71% of the teachers stated that the number of students enrolled in faculties of education should be reduced, 11.43% stated that the quality of education in faculties of education should be increased, and 20% stated that it is important to admit qualified students to faculties of education. The rate of participants who emphasized that teacher selection is also important in improving the reputation of teaching is 14.28%. For example, participant P31 emphasized merit and justice in teacher selection by saying, “ (...) I can make a suggestion in the form of teacher selection in accordance with merit.” Participant P14 said, “need and competence should be considered in appointments, and rights, justice and equality should be ensured in teaching.” One participant also stated that inadequate teachers should be weeded out.

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One of the suggestions for improving the reputation of the teaching profession is that senior administrators, school administrators and politicians should respect and value teachers. The percentage of participants expressing this view is 14.25%. 25.71% of the participants emphasized the importance of creating public awareness and public support. Among the participants who stated that the value of the teacher should be placed in the society with the support of the media and politicians, the participant coded P1 said that “the correct language about the teaching profession should be spread and an example should be set for the society”, and the participant coded P18 said “Raising public awareness is the most important element that will improve the reputation of teaching. I think it is very important that teaching has a respectable position and that it is recognized by the authorities that it has such a position.”

20% of the participants stated that deterrent measures should be taken through protective laws against negative behaviors against teachers. Participant P16 stated that “good sanctions should be imposed on those who disrespect teachers.” Participant P21 stated that violence against teachers should end. In relation to this, 8.57% of the participants recommended the development of a teaching profession law, and the participant coded P20 emphasized the importance of the profession law by saying “No right that is not protected by laws can spread to the base.” The participant coded P24 expressed his expectation regarding the regulation of the Teaching

Profession Law by saying “In this regard, the principles, aims, vision and mission of the teaching profession should be determined with clear statements and put into practice”.

Again, 20% of the participants emphasized that preventing the intervention of parents in education plays an important role in improving the reputation of teaching. For example, participant K6 said, “Parents should be restricted to understand that they cannot interfere with the teacher, and they should be restricted from having the opportunity to meet with teachers in any situation.” Participant P15 said, “Teacher-parent relations should be regulated, and parents should not be allowed to come to school waving their arms.” Similarly, participant K11 stated that parents should not be randomly admitted to the school and emphasized that parents should not think that the teacher is always accessible by saying “Personal phone numbers should not be available to parents”. Participant P13 also expressed his discomfort on this issue by saying, “I advocate that teachers' personal numbers should not be accessible to parents.”

Some participants expressed their discomfort with the view of the school as a place where the student is a distraction and the teacher is seen as the caretaker of children, and suggested that efforts should be made to change this view in society. The participant coded P10 stated that teachers should stop underestimating the work they do.

The rate of participants who think that improving personal and social rights is necessary to improve the reputation of teachers is 20%. 5.71% of the participants suggested that working conditions should be improved, and 8.57% suggested that regulations should be made to increase the authority of teachers and enable them to take initiative.

Maintaining discipline at school is also among the suggestions made by the participants. 11.43% of the participants stated that they thought that ensuring discipline at school would contribute to improving the reputation of the teacher. The participant coded P13 said, “(...) I think that teacher reputation starts with the student. Therefore, the necessary discipline and education should be given to the students first”, while the participant coded K1 stated that training on discipline should be given at school. The participant coded P27 emphasized the importance of discipline by saying “More effective disciplines should be applied in teacher-student and parent communication”.

In addition, one participant stated that teachers should be rewarded in front of the community, one participant stated that teachers should be involved in educational planning processes, and another participant stated that out-of-field responsibilities should be taken away from teachers.

4. Conclusion, Discussion and Recommendations

Conclusion and Discussion

While defining the concept of professional reputation, teachers emphasized the sub-elements of respectability, being valued and reliability. Sunar (2020) defined professional reputation as the social prestige of professions in his research on the reputation of professions. Similarly, Çelikten, Şanal, and Yeni (2005), Kıran, Durmuş, and Sucu (2019) emphasized the relationship between reputation and prestige in their studies. In this study, it is seen that most of the teachers included the concept of reputation while defining the concept of professional reputation. Baltaş (2013) underlined the relationship between reputation and reliability. In this context, it is seen that teachers are in an evaluation that overlaps with the literature on the concept of professional reputation and that they have sufficient knowledge and perception of this concept.

It is understood that teachers are divided into two about whether teaching is a reputable profession or not. The fact that approximately half of the participants stated that teaching is not a reputable profession is important in terms of teachers' evaluation of their profession. Among those who think that teaching is a prestigious profession, 44.44% stated that the prestige of the teaching profession has decreased compared to previous years. Similarly, 70.59% of the teachers who stated that teaching was not a prestigious profession stated that they believed that the teaching profession used to be prestigious, but today it is no longer prestigious. Based on this, it can be concluded that the majority of teachers have the opinion that the reputation of the teaching profession has decreased. The results of the studies on the reputation of professions conducted in 2015 and 2020 under the leadership of Lütfi Sunar reveal that the reputation of the teaching profession has shown a serious decline even within 5 years. In the 2015 survey, teaching ranked 4th among professions in terms of reputation, but in the 2020 survey, it dropped 10 places to 14th place. These findings are in line with teachers' responses emphasizing the decline in reputation. It is obvious that teachers have deeply felt the loss of professional reputation in society. Similarly, Kıran, Durmuş, and Sucu (2019) also stated in their study that teachers think that there is a negative attitude towards teachers in social life and that they stated that there has been a loss of reputation compared to previous years. In addition to these, teachers emphasized the role of the teaching profession in raising people and educating the society as a source of reputation for their profession, and underlined the characteristics of being a source of information and a reliable person. It is understood that teachers who think that the teaching profession is not prestigious cite the loss of prestige, problems arising from the system and administration, and social deterioration as the reasons for this discrediting. Similarly, Demir and Hammalı (2020) stated in their study that the change in social value judgments over time has an impact on professional reputation.

In the factors that positively affect teachers' reputation, factors related to teachers' personal characteristics were identified, and the most prominent factors were teachers' positive attitudes and behaviors, communication skills, knowledge and professional equipment, and fulfilling professional responsibilities by caring about the profession. In their study, Demir and Hammalı (2020) emphasized the importance of teachers' personal attitudes and behaviors in the formation of professional reputation.

Among the social and environmental factors that positively affect the reputation of the teaching profession, the most prominent factor is that teaching is a profession that affects the society. Favorable economic conditions and adequate wages, sharing good examples, teachers' supportive attitudes towards each other and professional solidarity are among the other environmental factors emphasized.

Among the factors that negatively affect the teaching profession, the most emphasized factor by teachers is the inadequacy of economic conditions and salaries. 42.85% of the teachers stated that teachers' salaries have decreased and this situation has decreased the value of teaching in the eyes of the society. It is stated in various studies that one of the main factors determining the reputation of teachers is the economic situation of teachers and that the inadequacy of the wages paid to teachers negatively affects the reputation of the profession (Çelikten, Şanal, & Yeni, 2005; Kıran, Durmuş, & Sucu, 2019; Demir & Hammalı, 2020). Participants who stated that teacher salaries in Turkey are low compared to other professions stated that low salaries reduce the reputation of the teaching profession. The participants who stated that the salaries received by teachers are insufficient stated that the society has established a link between economic power and reputation and therefore the reputation of the teaching profession is negatively affected. Although this result contradicts the result of Erden (2005) that “teacher salaries are low but the profession is reputable”, it is similar to the results of Arslanoğlu (1992); Süngü (2012); Kalin, Čepić, and Šteh (2017); Semerci, Eliüşük, and Kartal (2012), who found that low salaries reduce the reputation of the teaching profession. In fact, Sunar (2020) explained that there is a close relationship between the reputation of professions and their earnings, that high wages are one of the most sought-after features of a good job, and therefore, it is expected that professions with high earnings will have a higher reputation.

Another situation that teachers describe as an important factor that negatively affects professional reputation is the intervention of parents in education and their negative discourses. Teachers stated that the intervention of parents in teaching processes and the loss of the professional boundary between parents and teachers, especially in recent years, had a negative impact on teacher reputation, and that they were uncomfortable being accessible at all hours of the day, especially on

their personal phones, and that this situation was one of the factors that negatively affected teacher reputation (Demir & Hammalı, 2020).

Emphasizing the negative impact of the media on professional reputation, teachers listed the sharing of negative examples in the media, negative and even provocative discourses about teachers in the media among the factors that reduce the reputation of teaching. In their study, Demir and Hammalı (2020) stated that teachers' misbehaviors are more exaggerated and attracted more attention by the press, and that negative news with provocative titles such as “scandal in the classroom, violence against teachers, abusive teachers” reduce the reputation of the teaching profession. This situation is similar to the results of Altun (2014) and Kıran, Durmuş, and Sucu (2019) that the media has an impact on the reputation of the teaching profession and damages the reputation of the profession. In these studies, it was emphasized that the media portrayed all teachers as responsible and schools as places where problems are constantly experienced in the news about teachers, and that there has been an increase in the number of posts that create a negative impression on the teaching profession through social media, which has become widespread in recent years, and that these have caused a negative attitude towards teachers in society.

The high quotas of faculties of education, low entrance scores to faculties of education, low quality of students who prefer faculties of education, and the inadequacy of the quality of education given in faculties of education were also considered among the factors that caused the decline in teacher reputation. The fact that teaching is an easily obtainable profession and that people who are not graduates of education faculties are appointed and/or employed as teachers were also considered in this context. This result is in line with the results of Kavcar (2003), Çelikten, Şanal and Yeni (2005), Demir and Hammalı (2020), Gümüştas and Gülbahar (2022). Gümüştas and Gülbahar (2022) stated that education faculties should be made more attractive for more successful students to choose the teaching profession; Çelikten, Şanal, and Yeni (2005) stated that the admission of qualified and willing students to the teaching profession and the preference of young people who are successful in high school to teaching programs will contribute greatly to increasing the reputation of the teaching profession. Kavcar (2003) stated that “If everyone becomes a teacher, it means that teaching is not considered a profession” and criticized the appointment of graduates of different fields as teachers, even though the Basic Law on National Education defines teaching as a specialty profession. Kavcar (2003) also emphasized the importance of the quality of teaching staff in faculties of education and stated that the quality of teacher training academics should be increased.

As a result of the research, teachers stated that the negative language used by senior administrators and politicians about the teaching profession led to a decrease in the reputation of the profession.

Similarly, Demir and Hammalı (2020) stated that the negative statements made by Turkish Ministers of National Education and senior administrators about teachers and the teaching profession led to a decrease in the reputation of the teaching profession. In order to make teachers more valuable and respected in society, positive discourses should be increased (Gümüştaş & Gülbahar, 2022).

Another factor that negatively affects the reputation of the teaching profession is defined as teachers' negative attitudes and behaviors and their inability to keep up with the age by not fulfilling their professional responsibilities. The importance of teachers improving themselves and displaying a professional stance was emphasized. In the study conducted by Çelikten, Şanal and Yeni (2005), teachers expressed their dissatisfaction with their colleagues who could not keep up with the age. Demir and Hammalı (2020) also stated that negative attitudes and behaviors arising from teachers negatively affect professional reputation.

Violence and mobbing against teachers, inadequate personal rights and working conditions of teachers are among the factors emphasized by teachers.

Among the suggestions for improving the professional reputation of teachers, improving the economic conditions of teachers ranked first. Increasing the quality and quantity of teacher trainings, preventing the intervention of parents in education, creating public opinion through positive discourse and the widespread use of positive language, especially by senior administrators and politicians, and increasing the quality of education given in faculties of education by reducing student enrollment in faculties of education are among the prominent suggestions. It was emphasized that parents' interference in education should be prevented, personal and social rights and working conditions should be improved, professional and personal development should be supported, and teachers should be protected against negative behaviors against them through legal regulations. Ensuring discipline in schools was also among the suggestions made.

As a result, although teachers have been positioned in a respected place in society for many years, a significant loss of prestige has been observed in the teaching profession in recent years. Although the value given to the teacher is accepted as one of the important criteria in the construction of civilizations, it is seen that the reputation, dignity and social position of the teacher in the visible face of life do not coincide with what is expressed in theory. For this reason, it is necessary to ensure that teachers reach the level of prestige they deserve as soon as possible.

Recommendations

According to the research, it has been revealed that there are factors that negatively affect the reputation of the teaching profession compared to previous years. The factors affecting the reputation of the teaching profession positively and negatively were identified and suggestions were put forward for the factors affecting the reputation of the profession positively.

Recommendations for Practitioners

- Parents' interference in education should be prevented and the professional boundary between parents and teachers should be maintained. Communication with parents should be formalized and the teacher's personal and professional life should be prevented from interfering with each other. For example, the fact that parents have the teacher's personal number makes the teacher accessible to parents day and night.
- Efforts should be made to improve the salaries and wages of teachers. The budget allocated to education should be increased.
- Teachers' self-development should be encouraged and teachers should be motivated in this direction. For this purpose, qualified in-service trainings for the teaching profession should be provided, and trainings on professional ethics and professional attitudes as well as personal development should be offered.
- Policies should be put in place to increase discipline in schools.
- Teachers should be supported to participate in cultural, artistic and scientific activities in order to increase their knowledge, experience and equipment and to keep them up-to-date.
- The quotas of faculties of education should be reduced, the quality of students entering faculties of education should be increased, and efforts should be made to improve the quality of education provided by faculties of education.
- People who are not graduates of education faculties should be prevented from teaching, and qualified and qualified graduates should be appointed on a fair and merit-based basis.
- When formulating educational policies and in the statements and evaluations of senior administrators and policy makers, attention should be paid to include expressions that will reveal the value given to teachers and to use a common and exemplary positive language to create positive public opinion about teacher reputation.
- Legal arrangements should be made to prevent violence and intimidation (mobbing) against teachers, and the Law on the Profession of Teaching should be revised to include teacher dignity.
- Considering the impact of the media on society, it should be ensured that the media act more responsibly and meticulously in the news about teachers and avoid generalizations.

- Positive examples of the teaching profession should be shared more and teachers should be rewarded in public.
- Teachers should be provided with psychological support at regular intervals, and teachers should be ensured to be in a positive mental state.
- In-service training activities for teachers should be increased to support teachers' up-to-date training methods.

Recommendations for Researchers

- The effect of teacher-parent-student relationship on teacher reputation can be investigated. Since parents and students are the primary source of the perception of teacher reputation, it would be useful to obtain important information about professional reputation.
- In the literature, studies on teacher reputation have mostly been conducted on limited study groups. Conducting a more comprehensive study covering many regions and provinces will reveal the perception of teacher reputation more clearly.
- Studies in the literature have been conducted on teachers, and research evaluating teacher reputation from the perspective of parents or policy makers will help to reveal the current situation more clearly.
- The impact of teachers' personal attitudes on the reputation of the teaching profession can be comprehensively investigated and suggestions can be made on how professional responsibilities, ethical and moral attitudes should be.
- The effect of legal regulations, especially the Law on Teaching Profession, on the reputation of teaching profession should be investigated

5. REFERENCES

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